

"Green roofs and urban gardens as Biodiversity Corridors: Evidence from Birds and Arthropods Communities in Lisbon (Portugal)"

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Abstract

Green roofs are a type of Nature-Based Solution (NBS) in which built infrastructures, such as building rooftops or spaces above underground parking facilities, are partially or fully covered with vegetation. They provide well documented benefits for urban environments and human well-being, including rainwater retention, temperature regulation, air quality improvement, and economic benefits. However, research remains disproportionately focused on their functional and socio-economic benefits, with few studies examining the potential of green roofs to support urban biodiversity and their integration into the broader urban ecological network.

This study aims to contribute to filling this knowledge gap, by comparing the biodiversity found on green roofs with that of other two urban structures: urban gardens and areas with little to no vegetation (hereafter, grey areas). Biodiversity assessments were conducted on 11 green roofs and adjacent urban gardens and grey areas in Lisbon (Portugal). Traditional sampling methods were used, including point counts for birds and active search transects for arthropods. The results indicate that bird and arthropod communities on green roofs are comparable to those found in urban gardens. Both urban structures supported significantly higher richness and abundance than grey areas. However, community composition was similar across all urban structures. These findings contribute to a broader understanding of the ecological value of green roofs and highlight their potential to expand green spaces within urban landscapes, underscoring their importance for supporting biodiversity in urban environments.

Keywords: urban ecology, birds, arthropods, biodiversity conservation, nature-based solutions, urban green spaces, urban ecosystems

Introduction

It is estimated that, by 2050, 68% of the human population will live in urban areas (United Nations, 2018). This ongoing urban expansion leads to increased habitat fragmentation and destruction (Xiao *et al.*, 2020). The rhythm at which urbanization is expanding contributes to higher levels of pollution, resource depletion, rising temperatures, decline in biodiversity (Xing *et al.*, 2017), as well as community homogenization (McKinney, 2006). Together, these factors highlight the need for strategies that can support more sustainable urban growth.

Nature-based solutions (NBS) refer to actions designed to protect, sustainably manage, and restore ecosystems, whether natural or modified, while addressing societal challenges effectively and adaptively, and yielding benefits for both humanity and nature. (United Nations, 2022). As such, these solutions have emerged as key strategies for enhancing urban sustainability and liveability (Teotónio *et al.*, 2021, Xing *et al.*, 2017). In urban areas, some examples of NBS mentioned by the European Commission (2020) are the construction of green corridors, sustainable urban drainage systems, pollinator sites and green roofs. The European Commission has also highlighted that, in the specific context of urban areas NBS, including green roofs, “can bring additional and more diverse nature into cities”, although there are still some knowledge gaps regarding the impact of these infrastructures on urban fauna.

The term “green roof” is most commonly used when referring to the top of buildings that have

been partially or completely covered by a layer of vegetation (as well as other layers, like an impermeable membrane and growth medium for the vegetation) (Castleton *et al.*, 2010). But the term can in fact refer to any built infrastructure on top of which vegetation has been installed, even if at ground level (an example are green areas that have been built on top of underground parking structures). Green roofs have been shown to provide multiple benefits for urban sustainability, including temperature regulation, rainwater retention and improved air quality (Castleton *et al.*, 2010), along with economic benefits (Teotónio *et al.*, 2021), positive impact on human well-being through noise insulation (Connelly, 2015) and the creation of recreational spaces that are also aesthetically pleasing (Teotónio *et al.*, 2021, Xing *et al.*, 2017).

Williams *et al.* (2014) stated that it was premature to claim that green roofs had biodiversity benefits, and urged ecologists to work with the industry, to increase knowledge on the topic. Recently, Tiago *et al.* (2024) reported that, in the past decade and a half, there has been an increase of interest in the effects of green roofs and walls on biodiversity, but some knowledge gaps remain. For example, most of these studies compared animal communities in green roofs with those found on conventional roofs (Partridge & Clark, 2018; Washburn *et al.*, 2016) or in surrounding areas that vary in the proportion of green and grey spaces (Eakin *et al.*, 2015). However, others lack control sites (Fabián *et al.*, 2021) and do not directly compare green roofs with other types of green

spaces. This leaves a knowledge gap regarding how green roofs perform relative to more established green spaces, like urban gardens, which often have more diverse and complex vegetation structures. Tiago *et al.* (2024) also noted that most research on this topic has focused on arthropods and has been conducted predominantly in regions with a Temperate Continental Climate. For instance, no studies focusing on bird communities have been carried out in Mediterranean climates, and none in Portugal. In Spain, however, Benedito Durà *et al.* (2023) compared flying arthropod communities from one green roof, one conventional roof and two ground-level gardens. Moreover, most existing studies focused on either arthropods or birds, but few analyse these two groups simultaneously (Tiago *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, many studies concentrate in a single arthropod group, such as bees (Tonietto *et al.*, 2011), or only on a limited specific taxon (Braaker *et al.*, 2014). Exceptions include Fábian *et al.* (2021) in Argentina, who identified all sampled arthropods to the species level, and Partridge & Clark (2018) in the US, who worked with both birds and arthropods, comparing green roofs with conventional roofs in their vicinity.

Birds are a well-known animal group, widely used in ecological studies. This is due to the fact that most bird species are relatively easy to detect and observe, are widely distributed and are known to be good indicators of large-scale environmental changes, and thus quite useful to evaluate environmental quality/health (Mekonen, 2017). Specifically, in urban

environments, some studies have demonstrated that bird communities respond to various components of the urban matrix and can therefore serve as indicators of its ecological complexity. For example, more developed urban areas generally favour generalist species, and species richness tends to decrease with increasing levels of urban disturbance. In contrast urban green spaces are associated with higher levels of species richness and evenness (Ortega-Álvarez & MacGregor-Fors, 2009). When it comes to green roofs, a study done in the Midwestern USA suggested that green roofs may provide additional resources for bird communities and increase habitat connectivity, including during breeding season (Eakin *et al.*, 2015).

Arthropods are another animal group that is often used as an environmental indicator, since they are relatively easy to sample, are very diverse (including in ecological functions), and respond relatively quickly to environmental changes (McIntyre, 2000). Previous studies have already shown that arthropod richness generally declines with higher levels of urbanization (Fenoglio, 2020) and that increased surface imperviousness contributes to a reduced diversity, impacting insect orders like Hymenoptera and Lepidoptera, which include key pollinators (Fenoglio, 2020; Lagucki *et al.*, 2017). In urban environments, green roofs seem to complement existing green spaces and can be colonized by arthropod communities from nearby zones, especially larger green roofs and those installed in more vegetated urban landscapes (Fabián *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, it

has also been shown that, when compared to conventional roofs, green roofs have increased arthropod abundance (Partridge & Clark, 2018).

In Lisbon, previous studies on green roofs have primarily focused on the economic feasibility of their installation, highlighting well-known benefits such as thermal regulation, sound insulation, and aesthetic value (Teotónio, 2016, Cruz *et al.*, Melo *et al.*, 2020). However, less attention has been given to their impact on biodiversity. The city features a diverse array of green spaces, varying in size, vegetation types, and structural complexity. Green roofs may offer new possibilities for the implementation of more vegetated areas within the urban matrix of Lisbon, contributing to these corridors, especially because it was estimated that about 52% of the city's grey area had potential for green roof installation (Silva *et al.*, 2017).

The main objective of this study is to assess the role of green roofs in supporting bird and arthropod communities in Lisbon. More specifically, the study aims to compare the composition of these communities present on green roofs with those found in urban gardens and grey areas. We aim to test this hypothesis: Green roofs and urban gardens have similar taxonomic richness, while having significantly higher richness from grey areas.

2. Methods

2.1. Study Area

This study was carried out in Lisbon (Portugal). This city is a relatively densely populated European capital, with almost 550,000 inhabitants (INE, 2021). It is characterized by its urban environment and its Mediterranean climate (Kottek *et al.*, 2006, Peel *et al.*, 2007).

Sampling site selection was done through a two-set framework. Firstly, to determine which green roofs to sample, satellite images were analysed, and *in-situ* confirmation of the sites was done to assess their suitability for this study. The criteria for the choice of sites included accessibility (with preference given to publicly accessible sites), sufficient area for sampling, as well as the existence of adequate urban gardens and grey areas in their vicinity. Ultimately, a total of 11 green roofs across Lisbon were chosen for sampling (Figure 1). All of the sampled green roofs were constructed at ground level and accessible to the general public.

Fig. 1 – Map with the locations of the 11 sampled green roofs (red dots) within the city of Lisbon (Map created using the Free and Open Source QGIS).

2.4. Sampling

Secondly, given that the main objective of this study was to compare biodiversity patterns across different urban habitat types, urban gardens and grey areas were selected through the following criteria: (i) they had to be within a 250 m distance from their respective green roofs, (ii) urban gardens were considered vegetated areas that are not installed on building infrastructure (and as such are not classified as green roofs), and (iii) grey areas were zones with little to no vegetation (i.e., not necessarily devoid of vegetation but, when present, it was extremely sparse and/or existed in minimal quantities) (Figure S1).

The first sampling season was conducted from December 4 (2023) to February 7 (2024) (winter), and the second from April 10 to May 21, 2024 (spring). No sampling sessions were held on days with adverse weather conditions, such as rain and strong wind, as these conditions tend to affect the activity of both birds and arthropods, as well as the detection ability of the observer. Bird sampling usually started about two hours after sunrise, followed by arthropod sampling. In some cases, a waiting period was applied to ensure that arthropod surveys were carried out at a more suitable time of day. The number of sampling points/transects at each site was determined by the size of the sampling area and its vegetation characteristics. Sampling points were initially defined using satellite imagery (Google Maps, 2019), which were used to estimate sampling

site dimensions. This resulted in 38 bird point counts (14 on green roofs, 12 on urban gardens and 12 on grey areas), as well as 62 arthropod transects (23 on green roofs, 19 on urban gardens and 20 on grey areas; for details, see Table S1).

2.4.1. Birds

Birds were surveyed using 10-minute point counts. During each count, all individuals seen or heard were recorded. For every detection, the distance from the observer was noted as either within or beyond a 30-m radius. The 30-m radius was selected to match the spatial characteristics of the sampling sites, while allowing multiple non-overlapping point counts in larger sites.

Only birds actively using the sampled urban structures (green roofs, urban gardens, or grey areas) were included in the statistical analyses. Individuals were considered to be using the urban structure when observed perching, foraging, or interacting with vegetation or built structures within the sampled area. The exceptions were the swallows (Aves, Hirundinidae) that, despite not stopping on any of the sampled areas, were considered to be using the urban structure as they were seen feeding at a low height. Birds detected within the 30-m radius but not using the habitat (e.g., flying over the site) were excluded from statistical analyses. These individuals were recorded in a general species list (Table S2), which was particularly relevant in smaller

sampling areas. Bird identification was conducted *in situ* and, whenever possible, to the species-level. When species-level identification was not possible, individuals were identified to the genus-level (Supplementary Materials).

2.4.2. Arthropods

Arthropods were sampled along a 30-m transect using active-search. The number and placement of transects at each site were guided by the size of the sampled areas and the structure of the plant communities. Transects were spaced to avoid overlap and repeated observations, while also capturing the full diversity of vegetation strata present. All individuals observed within approximately one meter on either side of the transect were recorded. Specimens that could not be identified to the family-level *in situ* were captured using a 0.4-m diameter entomological sweep net and preserved in a 70% ethanol solution, for later identification in the laboratory.

All the collected arthropods were examined in the laboratory and identified to the lowest possible taxonomic level. This classification was done using appropriate identification keys for the various groups (Goulet & Huber, 1993; Choates, 1999; Marshall *et al.*, 2017; Thyssen, 2009). Any specimen not identified to the family-level was also not considered for the data analysis in this study. However, these individuals were recorded in a general list (Table S3).

2.6. Statistical Analysis

2.6.1. Taxonomic richness and abundance

Taxonomic richness and abundance were compared among habitat types (i.e., green roofs, grey areas, and urban gardens) and between seasons (i.e., winter and spring) using generalized linear mixed models (GLMMs). Models were fitted using the ‘lme4’ R-package (Bates *et al.*, 2015; for details, see Supplementary Materials). Because both response variables represent count data, models were specified with a Poisson error distribution and a log link function. Site and sampling point were included as nested random effects to account for spatial autocorrelation and the hierarchical sampling design. For abundance models only, taxonomic level was also included as an additional crossed random effect (i.e., species for birds and family for arthropods). Habitat type, season, and their interaction were included as fixed effects. Differences among groups were assessed by comparing model estimates and their 95% confidence intervals, with non-overlapping intervals interpreted as evidence of statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$).

2.6.2. Taxonomic composition and structure

Differences in taxonomic composition among sites were examined using three-dimensional non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS). Prior to ordination, community data were Hellinger-transformed to reduce the influence of highly abundant taxa. NMDS ordinations

were performed using the *metaMDS* function from the ‘vegan’ R-package (Oksanen *et al.*, 2025), based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarity (for details, see Supplementary Materials). Community differences among habitat types were formally tested using an Analysis of Similarities (ANOSIM) also based on Bray-Curtis distances, with 10,000 permutations. To aid interpretation of the ordination results, 95% confidence ellipses were calculated for each habitat type and overlaid on the NMDS plots. Ellipses were computed using the *stat_ellipse* function from the ‘tidyverse’ R-package (Wickham *et al.*, 2019) and represent the dispersion of sites within each group.

3. Results

3.1. General Results

A total of 36 bird species were recorded using the different habitats, with 27 of them in green roofs, 32 in urban gardens and 9 in grey areas (Table S4). The rock pigeon (*Columba livia*) was the most abundant species in every season and every habitat type. Regarding arthropods, a total of 75 families were identified, with 64 of them in green roofs, 49 in urban gardens, and 22 in grey areas (Table S5). Winter was mostly dominated by non-biting midges (Diptera, Chironomidae), whereas spring was dominated by ants (Hymenoptera, Formicidae) in both green roofs and urban gardens, whilst grey areas were dominated by mites (Acari, Erythraeidae).

3.2. Taxonomic richness and abundance

Taxonomic richness differed significantly among habitat types for both studied taxa (birds and arthropods; Figure 2a). In both cases, grey areas exhibited significantly lower taxonomic richness compared to the other two habitat types, namely green roofs and urban gardens. No significant differences in richness were detected between green roofs and urban gardens. For arthropods, season had a statistically significant effect on taxonomic

richness, with spring showing a significantly higher family richness than winter. With respect to abundance (Figure 2b), no statistically significant differences were detected among habitat types for either birds or arthropods. However, in the arthropod models, the random effect of family explained a substantial proportion of the variance in abundance. Additionally, season had a significant effect, with arthropod abundance being significantly higher in spring than in

Figure 2. Graphical representation of the results of the generalized linear mixed models (GLMMs). Panels on the left show the models related to birds, whereas panels on the right show the results of the models related to arthropods. Points represent the model estimates for each habitat type (i.e. green roofs, grey areas, and urban gardens), and lines indicate the 95% confidence intervals; when confidence intervals overlap, there is no statistically significant difference ($\alpha = 0.05$). Red indicates estimates for winter, while blue indicates estimates for spring. (a) Results for the models assessing taxonomic diversity. (b) Results for the models assessing abundance.

richness, with spring showing a significantly

winter.

3.3. Taxonomic composition and structure

Three-dimensional non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) ordination analyses suggested that neither bird nor arthropod communities were clearly distinct among habitat types (Fig. 3). Although some ANOSIM tests yielded statistically significant p-values, the consistently low R statistics indicate weak separation among groups. This interpretation is further supported by the strong overlap of confidence intervals among habitat types in the ordination space. Taken together, these results suggest that the observed statistical significance is more likely associated with high within-group variability rather than with meaningful differences in community composition or structure among habitat types.

Figure 3. Three-dimensional non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) ordination of sites based on community composition. The upper triangle shows the graphical representation of the NMDS ordinations, whereas the lower triangle presents the ANOSIM tests associated with the respective graphical representation. Points represent individual sites coloured by habitat type (i.e. green roofs, grey areas, and urban gardens). Ellipses indicate 95% confidence intervals. (a) Results for birds. (b) Results for arthropods.

4. Discussion

This study provides new empirical evidence on the ecological value of green roofs within Mediterranean urban environments. The results indicate that green roofs support bird and arthropod communities with levels of taxonomic richness comparable to those observed in urban gardens, while grey areas consistently showed lower biodiversity levels. Green roofs seem to be capable of contributing not only to climate adaptation, but also to urban biodiversity. Thus, these findings reinforce the growing recognition of green roofs as a relevant NBS.

The most abundant bird species recorded was consistent with expectations, as the rock pigeon was the most abundant in every habitat, and is very well adapted to urban environments (Przybylska et al., 2012). Regarding arthropod results, the ants (Formicidae) are the most abundant arthropod group in almost every habitat type in both seasons (with the exception of green roofs in winter). Although no particular reason was found for this, Benedito Durà *et al.* (2023) also found ants to not be among the most abundant taxa in the green roofs sampled in their work. The high abundance of sidewalk mites (*Balaustium* sp.; Erythraeidae) in grey areas in spring is corroborated by previous studies, as they seem to be adapted to high heat tolerance and requirement of a dry habitat makes dry sunny sites (i.e., exposed areas of asphalt or concrete) ideal for them (Hedges et al., 2013).

4.1. Taxonomic richness and abundance

The similarity in taxonomic richness between green roofs and urban gardens suggests that vegetated infrastructures installed on built environments can provide ecological conditions comparable to those found in more traditional green spaces. Previous studies have already demonstrated that vegetated urban habitats generally support higher biodiversity than highly urbanized areas (Órtega-Álvarez & MacGregor-Fors, 2009; Liordos *et al.*, 2021; Partridge & Clark, 2018). The present results extend this evidence by showing that, even when installed on artificial structures, vegetated habitats can sustain communities similar to those found in urban gardens.

This pattern is particularly relevant in dense cities where space for new ground-level green areas is limited. In such contexts, green roofs may represent an effective strategy to increase vegetated surfaces within the urban matrix without competing with other land uses (Silva *et al.*, 2017). As suggested by Eakin *et al.* (2015), these structures can provide additional habitat and resources for urban bird communities, potentially contributing to increased habitat availability and connectivity across urban landscapes.

The contrast observed between vegetated habitats (green roofs and urban gardens) and grey areas further highlights the ecological importance of vegetation in cities. Grey areas provide fewer resources for wildlife and typically support simplified communities dominated by a small number of urban-tolerant

species (McKinney, 2006). In contrast, even relatively simple vegetated habitats appear capable of supporting richer communities of birds and arthropods (Liordos *et al.*,2021).

To some taxa such as arthropods, other factors like climate might also play an important role. In fact, the most important factor shaping arthropod diversity was the season. This is a clear contrast with the response seen in birds. Nevertheless, several works describe how differences in photoperiod and food availability (both lower in winter) affect insect diapause and thus, their activity (Numata & Shintani, 2023).

Despite the differences in richness, no statistically significant differences in abundance were detected among habitat types. This pattern may reflect the high heterogeneity among sampling sites, which was captured in the random effects included in the models. Urban habitats are often highly variable in terms of vegetation structure, maintenance regimes, surrounding land use and connectivity to other green areas, all of which may influence local abundance patterns.

4.2. Taxonomic composition and structure

Community composition analyses indicated a strong overlap among habitat types, suggesting that species assemblages present on green roofs, urban gardens and grey areas largely originate from the same urban species pool. This pattern likely reflects the ability of many

urban species to use multiple habitat types within the urban landscape.

In this context, green roofs may function less as completely distinct ecological habitats and more as additional habitat patches integrated within the urban ecological network. By increasing the availability of vegetated surfaces within built environments, they may contribute to expanding habitat area and facilitating the movement of species across fragmented urban landscapes (Tiago *et al.*,2024).

The overlap in community composition may also reflect similarities in habitat structure among some sampling sites. Some grey areas included small amounts of vegetation, while certain green roofs and urban gardens were relatively small or structurally simple. Such structural similarities can reduce differences in community composition (Partridge & Clark, 2022), particularly for mobile taxa such as birds and many arthropods.

4.3. Limitations and implications for future research

Conducting biodiversity research in urban environments inevitably involves methodological and logistical constraints. The arthropod sampling method used in this study represented a compromise between collecting sufficient ecological data and minimizing disturbance in publicly accessible urban spaces. However, the approach primarily targeted visible and vegetation-associated taxa,

potentially underrepresenting ground-dwelling or cryptic arthropod groups.

Another limitation concerns taxonomic resolution. Arthropods were identified to the family level, which is common in broad biodiversity surveys (McIntyre, 2000) but may mask species-level ecological differences. Future research could benefit from higher taxonomic resolution or from the inclusion of functional trait analyses, allowing a better understanding of how green roofs contribute to ecosystem functioning in urban environments.

The time of bird sampling ideally occurs at earlier hours to capture peak activity periods, so later sampling may obscure differences that could reveal more detailed ecological patterns in the different habitat types. Possible lack of statistical independence between sites (maximum distance of 250 m, as mentioned in Methods) may also conceal further distinction between the communities of the different habitats.

In addition, future studies should investigate how specific characteristics of green roofs influence their biodiversity value. Factors such as roof size, vegetation composition, plant species origin, structural complexity and maintenance regimes have been shown to influence biodiversity in urban habitats (Beninde *et al.*, 2015; Paker *et al.*, 2014; Threlfall *et al.*, 2017), and even small green spaces can help promote biodiversity within cities (Liordos *et al.*, 2021). Landscape context is also likely to play an important role, as proximity to other green areas (including green

roofs) can facilitate colonization and movement of species across the urban matrix (Chamberlain *et al.*, 2007; Braaker *et al.*, 2014).

Understanding how these variables interact will be essential for designing green roofs that maximize biodiversity benefits while also contributing to other ecosystem services provided by NBS.

5. Final Remarks

This study provides the first assessment of faunal communities associated with green roofs in Portugal and the first to examine bird communities in these habitats under Mediterranean climatic conditions. The results demonstrate that green roofs can support biodiversity levels comparable to those found in urban gardens and substantially higher than those observed in highly urbanized areas.

These findings highlight the potential of green roofs to increase available habitat within dense urban environments and to complement existing green spaces. By introducing vegetated surfaces into built infrastructures, green roofs can contribute to expanding urban ecological networks and improving habitat availability for wildlife.

From an urban planning perspective, these results support the idea that green roofs should be considered as part of a broader system of urban green infrastructure rather than isolated ecological features and reinforce the relevance of integrating biodiversity considerations into

the design and implementation of green roofs as Nature-Based Solutions. When strategically implemented across cities, they may complement existing green spaces and contribute to strengthening ecological networks within urban environments, and incorporating native plant species, promoting structurally diverse vegetation and considering landscape connectivity may enhance the ecological performance of these infrastructures.

As urbanization continues to intensify worldwide, the integration of biodiversity-supporting infrastructures such as green roofs may become increasingly important for reconciling urban development with biodiversity conservation and ecosystem functioning in cities.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

MR received funding from the GRAVITY project (2022.02093.PTDC; <https://doi.org/10.54499/2022.02093.PTDC>).

PT received funding from the Scientific Employment Stimulus program (CEECIND2/02515/2021; <https://doi.org/10.54499/2021.02515.CEECIN> [D/CP1654/CT0006](https://doi.org/10.54499/2021.02515.CEECIN)). AIL received a contract

through the DL program (57/2016/CP1479/CT0008;

<https://doi.org/10.54499/DL57/2016/CP1479/CT0008>). This work was developed as a part of

the GRAVITY project (2022.02093.PTDC; <https://doi.org/10.54499/2022.02093.PTDC>)

and the GALLERY project (2023.18276.ICDT; <https://doi.org/10.54499/2023.18276.ICDT>),

funded by FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P., promoted by Instituto

Superior Técnico (IST), in collaboration with Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade de

Lisboa (Ciências ULisboa). MR, AIL, PT and AB want to acknowledge FCT – Fundação para

a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P. for the financial support to CE3C (UID/00329/2025;

<https://doi.org/10.54499/UID/00329/2025>) and CHANGE (LA/P/0121/2020;

<https://doi.org/10.54499/LA/P/0121/2020>),

through national funds, and the co-funding by the FEDER, within the PT2020 Partnership

Agreement and Compete 2020. CMS wants to acknowledge FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e

a Tecnologia, I.P. for the financial support to CERIS (UID/6438/2025;

<https://doi.org/10.54499/UID/06438/2025>)

through national funds, and the co-funding by the FEDER, within the PT2020 Partnership Agreement and Compete 2020.

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